

THE ROLE OF TITLE-INTERTEXT IN LITERARY TEXTS

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One of the most important tools for understanding a literary text is its title. The title is the name given to the article based on the internal content of the material. In fact, the name of the works and articles is inextricably linked with the content and essence, character and characteristics, subject and sign of the material covered. The more perfect, impressive and correct the title is, the more it will ensure the future success of the work. And the use of intertexts as titles is a double success of the fiction text. In literary texts, a part of proverbs, the name of a famous work or its characters, verses of poetic texts are used as title-intertext. If they express the artistic intention of the author, ensure the originality of the text construction, they affect the process of meaningful perception of the text for the reader. So, we can classify the intertextual sources that are chosen as titles in artistic texts as follows: 1. Poetry fragments; 2. Prose quotations; 3. Quotations from famous songs; 4. Titles of works of art Titles of national and foreign films; 5. Proverbs, sayings and expressions as titles from intertexts for literary texts.

There is also a specific way of using it. It can be conditionally divided into three:

1) get the finished text without any changes, 2) shorten the text, 3) add an addition. Although proverbs are rarely used as titles in literary texts, their specific functions are very important for the text and its content. If we look at examples of Uzbek literature, the use of proverbs as titles is often found in Gafur Gulam's work. Most of Gafur Gulam's stories are based on jokes and humor, but in fact, there are criticisms and bitter truths under them. The author chooses titles for such stories

from folk proverbs and sayings. The chosen title alone tells the reader a lot about the story. In general, it is stated in the researches that the titles of the artistic text should be chosen from the language units with wide emotional and expressive possibilities, based on the requirements of its various genres. The use of intertext types as a title also allows the title to express its textual content and to highlight its emotional and expressive potential. It should be mentioned here that intertextuality is the reader's understanding of the coded meaning. Therefore, the titles chosen as intertext should be familiar texts for the general public, otherwise communicative failure will occur in the process of understanding the text. It is also common to use the names of famous works of art and their characters as titles in poetic texts. In particular, Abdulla Qadiriyya's novel "Past Days" and its characters Kumush, Otabek, Zainab are chosen as the title of a specific poem, and the content of this poem is formed directly based on the title. In the works of poets such as Muhammad Yusuf and Iqbal Mirza, you can find many texts with such titles.

The intertext chosen as a title has another function in the literary text, and often such texts are parodies of the texts to which the intertext refers. That is, the author uses the title of a specific text created before him or a word or sentence from it as a title, and creates his own text in comparison to that work. The poem "Boshindadir" below, taken as an experiment, was also created in this way, and the radif of Navoiy's famous ghazal was included in the title and humorously written as a parody of it:

O‘n sakkiz ming olam oshubi
Padar boshindadir,
Neajab, chun o‘g‘li oning
O‘n sakkiz yoshindadir.
Nay misol shim kiygan ul
Sandiqdayin tufli bilan,
Hurpayib turgan savatdek
Soch aning boshindadir.

The title of this poetic text is an intertext, and its first line is also a quote from a famous ghazal. In the course of the poem, it can be seen that rhyming words taken from ghazals, such as in the beginning and in the youth, are used as rhymes. The reader will understand why the author chose such a title as soon as he reads the first verse of the poem. While parodying a famous ghazal, the author tries to give the exact opposite meaning to its content in the same form. More than 50% of the participants of the experiment evaluated this poetic text as a parody, simile, and parable of Navoiy's ghazal, and interpreted and perceived its content on this basis.

Most of the participants focused their attention not on Navoiy's ghazal, but on his commentary based on the words of the poetic text. "...either the current fashion or the old fashion, a young man who became a young father at the age of 18, criticized, maybe because of his desperation, his clothes and hair are in the same condition (he is not yet ready for marriage, or he has not started a family)." "... As a person grows older, his worries become bigger. An example of this is Father and Son. Youthful imagination is only suitable for youth. Or dressing as in the poem is only suitable for 18-year-olds. "... Only their fathers care about the future and problems of today's youth. And they themselves live according to the author's satirical similes - in the style of a poet, lightheartedness."

Thus, intertexts given as headings direct the reader to the content of the text, by which we mean both texts. That is, the text that is familiar to the reader is first perceived, and then the content of the given original text is perceived by combining it with the previous perception. Through this process, the reader gets a deeper understanding of the author's intention, the idea of the given text.

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